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Group 5: Health systems readiness for malaria elimination and eradication

Title

Health systems and global progress towards malaria elimination 2000-2016

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8 **Abstract**

9 **Background:** As more countries progress towards malaria elimination, a better understanding
10 of the most critical health system features for enabling and supporting malaria control and
11 elimination is needed.

12 **Methods:** All available health systems data relevant for malaria control were collated from 23
13 online data repositories. Principal component analysis was used to create domain specific
14 health system performance measures. Multiple regression model selection approaches were
15 used to identify key health systems predictors of progress in malaria control in the 2000-2016
16 period among 105 countries. Additional analysis was performed within malaria burden
17 groups.

18 **Results:** There was large heterogeneity in progress in malaria control in the 2000-2016
19 period. In univariate analysis, several health systems factors displayed a strong positive
20 correlation with reductions in malaria burden between 2000 and 2016. In multivariable
21 models, delivery of routine services and hospital capacity were strongly predictive of
22 reductions in malaria cases, especially in high burden countries. In low-burden countries
23 approaching elimination, primary health center density appeared negatively associated with
24 progress while hospital capacity was positively correlated with eliminating malaria.

25 **Conclusions:** The findings presented in this manuscript suggest that strengthening health
26 systems can be an effective strategy for reducing malaria cases, especially in countries with
27 high malaria burden. Potential returns appear particularly high in the area of service delivery.

28 **Keywords:** malaria, health systems, elimination

29 **Background**

30 To achieve a world free of malaria, health systems in malaria endemic countries face a series
31 of challenges: they need to identify populations at risk, cover at-risk populations with effective
32 preventive interventions, accurately diagnose and report cases, and treat malaria patients with
33 timely and high-quality care. Constraints to delivery of essential services not only cause
34 inefficiencies, but can also hinder progress in malaria control [1–3]. Deficiencies in national
35 health and surveillance systems likely contributed to the failure of the Global Malaria
36 Eradication Programme 50 years ago [4]. As a result of lessons learned, ongoing elimination
37 and eradication initiatives for other diseases have made a more purposeful effort to utilize and
38 build upon existing service delivery mechanisms [5,6], and the WHO’s Global Technical
39 Strategy for Malaria now recommends that national strategic plans consider health systems
40 readiness to expand malaria programs [7]. The recent renewed enthusiasm for malaria
41 eradication [8–10] has rekindled the dialogue and interest in whether present-day health
42 systems are prepared for this bold endeavor [11].

43 Health system strength generally has not been a primary consideration in decisions to
44 launch disease eradication programs, which have traditionally focused on biological and
45 technical factors, as well as costs and political will [12,13]. Research and discourse on this topic
46 has primarily focused on understanding the effects that vertical programs have had on health
47 systems [14,15] and on outlining approaches to ensure that eradication activities confer
48 maximum benefits to health systems while maintaining overall programmatic goals [13,16]. In
49 2010, several studies were published on the technical and operational feasibility of malaria
50 elimination. Most of these studies focused on strategies and needs for interrupting transmission,
51 and on assessing countries’ ability to create effective national malaria programs at scale [17–
52 21]. The recent Lancet Commission on Malaria Eradication proposes an ambitious target of
53 eradicating malaria by 2050. This report recognizes that a successful program will need to
54 strengthen health systems capacity by increasing human resources and developing management

55 competency at the provincial level, but highlights that historically malaria elimination has been
56 achieved in many countries well before health systems have provided universal coverage [9].

57 To date, however, there has been limited quantitative analysis of the role of health
58 systems in prior malaria control efforts, and for elimination programs in particular. Measuring
59 health systems performance is complex given the multidimensional nature of these systems and
60 the variable importance of these dimensions in different contexts [22–24]. Over the last 15 years
61 more data on health systems have become available at the global level, expanding our ability to
62 characterize and compare health systems across countries. The main objective of this study was
63 to utilize these datasets to empirically assess which aspects of health systems have been most
64 predictive of progress towards malaria elimination from 2000 to 2016.

65 **Methods**

66 The conceptual approach for this study focused on identifying characteristics of health systems
67 most predictive of progress in malaria control conditional on contextual factors, and is presented
68 in **Additional File 1: Analytical Framework**. Contextual factors included the level of
69 development of the country, initial malaria burden and broad resource availability to control for
70 level of investments in the health sector. This framework was developed through review and
71 feedback during meetings of the Strategic Advisory Group on malaria eradication in 2018-9.

72 *Data sources*

73 All available country-level information on health systems in the 2000-2016 period was
74 extracted and combined in a new health system database. A total of 23 online data repositories
75 related to malaria control and health systems were reviewed for relevant variables, including
76 the World Development and Governance Indicators, the WHO Global Health Observatory, the
77 World Bank Health Nutrition and Population database and country-level data provided
78 through the Measure DHS program [25–32]. **Additional File 2** gives a full list of all data
79 sources for which variables were reviewed for inclusion in the analysis.

80 *Predictor variable identification and classification*

81 A total of 83 health systems variables were grouped broadly into six categories
82 following the building blocks of the WHO health system framework: health system financing,
83 health service delivery, access to medicines, health system workforce and capacity,
84 governance, and information systems [22]. Additionally, 35 macroeconomic, demographic
85 and geographic indicators relevant for health systems and malaria control were reviewed for
86 inclusion in the analysis as control variables. Variables covering less than 50% of the core
87 sample of 105 malaria endemic countries were excluded from the analysis, and variables were
88 also qualitatively reviewed for inclusion based on relevance to the analytical framework, as
89 well as redundancy with other variables. **Additional File 3** provides an overview of domain
90 coverage for all variables reviewed for inclusion in our analysis, and **Additional File 4** gives
91 full definitions for all variables included in the analysis. Period averages for health systems
92 variables were computed across the 2000-2016 period.

93 *Outcome variables*

94 In general, the outcome used for our regressions was the relative reduction in malaria
95 cases per 1000 population (for *P.falciparum* and *P.vivax* combined) over the 2000-2016
96 period, obtained from the World Malaria Report [33]. Malaria incidence, rather than
97 mortality, was used because it better aligned with our primary question of interest on progress
98 towards elimination. In addition, many of the malaria mortality statistics published in the
99 World Malaria Report are modelled by applying a static case fatality of 0.256%, thus
100 containing limited information beyond the underlying case data [33]. In the absence of
101 reliable mortality data, parasite prevalence reductions could have been a viable alternative in
102 principle. However, this was not possible in practice because parasite prevalence estimates
103 are modelled using several health systems covariates as inputs, including health expenditure,
104 antenatal care coverage, immunization coverage, and treatment seeking behavior [34,35]. The
105 primary outcome considered in this analysis was thus the reduction in the number of malaria
106 cases per 1000 people over the 2000-2016 period. Among low burden countries (<1 case per

107 1000 in 2000), we also analyzed a binary proxy for elimination of whether the country
108 reached 0 cases by 2016, using unadjusted surveillance data [33].

109 *Preliminary (Single Variable) Analysis*

110 In a first step, all health systems variables (period averages) extracted for inclusion in
111 the analysis were correlated individually in unadjusted and adjusted regressions with absolute
112 reductions in malaria cases between 2000 and 2016 as the outcome. Adjusted regressions
113 controlled for initial level of development as measured by the Human Development Index
114 (HDI) – an indicator which includes income, education, and life expectancy – and level of
115 malaria burden (low, medium, or high) in 2000 [32]. Regressions adjusted for HDI were also
116 performed separately within the three malaria burden categories.

117 *Data consolidation*

118 Given that several variables were identified as proxies for the same health system
119 aspects or concepts, health system variables were consolidated into core domains for our main
120 analysis. These domains were broadly defined using the WHO building block framework [22]
121 except that health financing variables were considered as a contextual factor rather than a proxy
122 of health system functioning because they generally capture broad resource availability
123 **[Additional File 1]**. Using the final health systems dataset, any remaining missing data at the
124 country level were imputed using multiple imputation chained equations. **Additional File 7**
125 shows descriptive statistics for all 35 health systems variables in the original and imputed
126 datasets. Principal component analysis was then used to consolidate the available data within
127 each domain into core components of health systems. In cases where the first principal
128 component accounted for the majority of total domain variation observed (>50%), only the first
129 component was retained. If the first component explained less than 50%, additional
130 subcomponents were constructed until more than half of variation in each component was
131 accounted for. Composite “health systems scores” were generated by grouping countries into
132 deciles for each component and summing deciles across domains.

133 *Main analysis*

134 First, health systems scores (summed scores and rankings of countries by their scores)
135 were plotted against progress in malaria control. In addition, the health systems features of
136 countries performing at the top and bottom of their respective burden categories were visually
137 compared.

138 To identify the most predictive health system components for successful malaria
139 control conditional on initial malaria burden, initial HDI, and average total health expenditure
140 as percentage of GDP during 2000-2016, three empirical approaches were used: (1) standard
141 regression models including all 7 health systems components in the regression independent of
142 the strength of their association with progress in malaria control, (2) backward stepwise
143 selection (chosen among iterative search methods because it performed the best in terms of
144 residual error and parsimony, as described further in **Additional File 9**), (3) a systematic
145 combinatoric approach which searched through every possible combination of the 7
146 components (127 regressions in all) to minimize residual error. All models were estimated
147 using linear regression with heterogeneity-robust standard errors [36,37].

148 Given that the relative importance of specific health system factors likely varies across
149 different stages of malaria control, separate models for countries with high initial incidence
150 (≥ 300 cases per 1000 in 2000), moderate initial incidence (1-299 cases per 1000 in 2000)
151 and low initial incidence (< 1 case per 1000 in 2000) were fitted.

152 **Results**

153 As of 2000, malaria existed primarily in low and lower-middle income countries. As Figure 1
154 illustrates, 61 out of the 105 countries with at least one malaria case after 2000¹ were
155 classified as low-income, and 30 of these countries were classified as lower-middle income.
156 Table 1 gives an overview of baseline and average malaria case burden and development level
157 in the 2000-2016 period. Mean GDP per capita in this group increased from \$4404 to \$8454
158 during this period,² and countries on average reduced their case burden by 60% (Table 1).

159 ¹ These countries align with the “106 malaria-endemic countries” detailed in the Lancet Commission
 160 on Malaria Eradication with the exception of Kazakhstan, which did not have cases after 2000 [9,33].
 161 ² Currency is expressed in 2018 international US Dollars, Purchasing Power Parity
 162

163 **Figure 1: Initial burden of malaria by country income group**

164

165 **Notes:** Figure 1 shows the initial distribution of the 105 sample countries with respect to World Bank
 166 Income Category and initial malaria burden.

167

168 **Table 1: Descriptive statistics for countries with at least one case of malaria after 2000,**

169 **2000-2016 (N=105)**

	Baseline (2000)		Endline (2016)	
	Mean	95% CI	Mean	95% CI
Malaria cases per 1000	131.6	(97.9, 165.3)	78.8	(55.1, 102.5)
GDP_{pc}, PPP[†]	\$4402.5	(\$3290.6, \$5514.5)	\$8453.5	(\$6724.0, \$10,183.0)
HDI[*]	51.8	(49.0, 54.6)	60.0 [‡]	(57.5, 62.5)

Notes:

[†]GDP per capita in 2018 international \$, Purchasing Power Parity

^{*}Human Development Index (HDI) is based on GDP, life expectancy and education.

[‡]HDI endline data is from 2015, the last year available in this dataset.

170

171 *Individual health systems variables and progress in malaria control*

172 Out of 51 unique health system and financing variables identified, 26 variables showed
 173 statistically significant associations ($p < .05$) with reduction in malaria cases from 2000-2016
 174 in univariate models. However, when we adjusted the models for initial malaria burden and

175 HDI in 2000, only five variables displayed statistically significant associations with progress
 176 in malaria control: measles immunization coverage, TB treatment success rate, coverage of
 177 insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) among the high risk population, children with fevers seeking
 178 care in the public sector, and malaria surveillance reporting completeness. **Additional File 5**
 179 summarizes these results. When stratifying the adjusted models by initial burden of malaria,
 180 we saw the strongest associations in the highest burden group (>300 cases per 1000) across
 181 four domains: overall health and malaria-specific financing, health service delivery, access to
 182 medicines, and health workforce and capacity [**Additional File 6**]. Among high burden
 183 countries only, the following health spending variables displayed positive correlations with
 184 reductions in malaria burden: percent of total health expenditure which is from foreign aid;
 185 external malaria financing per capita; and external malaria financing allocated specifically for
 186 ITNs, treatment, diagnosis, and health system strengthening.

187 *Principal Component Analysis*

188 Table 2 shows the results of our principal component analyses within each domain of
 189 health systems, and **Additional File 7** gives the full details and descriptive statistics for each
 190 of the variables included for each domain. A total of 7 principal health system components
 191 were identified, ranging from health service delivery to health information systems.

192 **Table 2: Health Systems Components identified in Principal Component Analysis (PCA)**

No.	Name of component	No. Variables Included	% of domain variance explained
1	Health service delivery, routine services	6	60.1%
2	Access to medicines	2	68.3%
3	Health workforce	3	74.6%
4	Health system capacity: basic health centers	2	91.6%
5	Health system capacity: hospital capacity	2	56.1%
6	Governance	8	64.8%
7	Health information systems	2	74.2%

193

194 *Health Systems Scores*

195 Total health system scores—the sum of the decile ranks in the seven domains—ranged
196 from 10 in the country with the weakest health system (Chad) to 69 in the country with the
197 strongest health system (South Korea). This overall score displayed a strong (and mostly
198 linear) relationship with countries' HDI in 2000 (Figure 2).

199 **Figure 2: Health systems score and initial level of development in 2000**

200

201 **Notes:** Figure 2 shows kernel-weighted local polynomial smoothed relationship between the Human
202 Development Index and total health systems scores.

203

204 Health systems scores were also strongly correlated with progress in malaria control
205 between a health systems score of approximately 30 and 60, though the relationship was less
206 strong towards the ends of the scale (Figure 3).

207 **Figure 3: Health systems score and percent reduction in malaria incidence, 2000-2016**

208

209 **Notes:** Figure 3 shows kernel-weighted local polynomial smoothed relationship between Reduction in
210 Malaria cases, 2000-2016 and total health systems scores.

211
212 When comparing the distribution of health systems scores of countries which reached 0 cases
213 of malaria versus those which did not (Figure 4), there were no obvious differences for the
214 low burden category, which had average health systems scores of 51 and 47, respectively. In
215 the middle burden group, differences in health systems scores were substantial: the median
216 health system score among countries reaching zero cases was 51, compared with 29 in the
217 group which did not eliminate malaria. In the high burden group, no countries reached 0 cases
218 by 2016, but countries on average scored more poorly on health systems compared with
219 countries with lower initial burden.

220 **Figure 4: Health Systems Score for countries which eliminated malaria versus those that**
221 **did not, by burden category (“Yes”= reached 0 cases, “No” = did not reach 0 cases)**

222
223 **Notes:** Figure 4 shows distribution of health systems scores by baseline burden and the likelihood of
224 reaching 0 cases by 2016. In the first group (< 1 case per 1000 initially), 14 countries (50% of
225 countries in this group) reached 0 cases; in the second group (1-300 cases), the same was achieved by
226 3 countries (6%), and in the third group (>300 cases) no countries reached 0 cases.

227
228 When plotting change in malaria cases over time according to the ranking of the health
229 system score of the county, large heterogeneity in progress can be observed across burden
230 levels and health system scores (Figure 5). In general, low burden countries at baseline
231 appeared to have relatively strong health systems while high burden countries appeared to

232 have lower ranking health systems. Within the high burden category, the funnel shape of the
233 arrows seems to indicate that more highly ranked health systems made greater progress in
234 malaria control compared with weaker systems. There were some remarkable departures from
235 the trend: five countries increased in malaria, including Rwanda which increased by 95%
236 despite having a mid-ranked health system [Additional File 8]. Our literature search to better
237 understand Rwanda's increase in cases showed a potential gap in usage of effective
238 interventions, e.g. due to pest infestation and perception about their control [38]; fortunately,
239 Rwanda declined in cases from 2016 to 2017, a positive sign that this trend may be reversing
240 [39]. In addition, there were substantial malaria reductions in countries with health systems
241 ranked on the poorest end of the spectrum across all burden categories, including Bangladesh
242 (BGD, 94%), South Sudan (SSD, 43%), and Democratic Republic of Congo (COD, 42%).

243 **Figure 5: Ranking of Health Systems Score and change in malaria incidence, 2000-2016**
244

245

246 **Notes:** Low burden countries (< 1 case per 1000 in 2000), middle burden (1-300 cases in 2000), high
 247 burden (>300 cases per 1000 in 2000). Full country labels and rankings provided in Additional File 8.

248

249 “Best and worst performers” analysis

250

When comparing health systems features of countries with major reductions in malaria

251

incidence to those of countries with less progress, substantial differences were found.

252

Figure 6 shows the health systems scores of highest and lowest performers in terms of

253

percentage reduction in the burden of malaria in the high initial burden group. Health systems

254

scores for top performers (Guinea-Bissau, Solomon Islands and Burundi) were overall higher

255

in almost all domains than the health system scores for bottom performers (Niger, Mali and

256

Guinea), though low performers appeared to have reasonably good basic facility coverage.

257 **Figure 6: Health Systems dimensions for highest and lowest performers for relative**
 258 **change in malaria cases, 2000-2016 among high burden countries (300+ cases per 1000**
 259 **population)**
 260

261
 262 Figure 7 compares health systems scores of highest and lowest performers among middle
 263 burden countries in 2000. The three most successful countries in this category were Sri Lanka,
 264 Paraguay and Tajikistan: all three achieved a 100% reduction in malaria cases, and all had
 265 total health systems scores >45. The low performers had a more complex story. Venezuela
 266 scored well on staffing, service delivery, and data systems, but had a political and economic
 267 situation that deteriorated after 2012 leading to a severe malaria outbreak [40]. Rwanda scored
 268 reasonably well in terms of overall health system (score of 39), but regardless experienced a
 269 massive increase in malaria burden after 2012. In comparison, Eritrea also experienced an
 270 increase in cases but scored poorly on health systems (score of 24).

271 **Figure 7: Health Systems dimensions for highest and lowest performers for relative**
 272 **change in malaria cases, 2000-2016 among middle burden countries (1-300 cases per**
 273 **1000 population)**

275

276 Among low burden countries, little difference was found in the health systems scores between
 277 the “highest” and “lowest” performers (Figure 8); however, every country in this category
 278 made large progress towards malaria elimination. The weakest performer in this group was
 279 Panama which reduced cases by 44.3%. **Additional File 8** provides progress estimates as well
 280 as health systems scores for all countries.

281 **Figure 8: Health Systems dimensions for highest and lowest performers for relative**
 282 **change in malaria cases, 2000-2016 among low burden countries (<1 case per 1000**
 283 **population), excluding 14 countries which reached 0 cases**

284

285 *Combined Health System Regression Results*

286 Table 3 shows the main variable selection and regression results using outcomes of percent
 287 reduction in cases from 2000-2016 (“malaria control”) and probability of reaching 0 cases by
 288 2016 among low burden countries (“malaria elimination”). Full model results including p-
 289 values are presented in **Additional File 10**. Columns 1 of Table 3 shows results for a basic
 290 regression model including all 7 components; columns 2 and 3 show results based on selected
 291 variables. The overall predictive power was weak for all malaria control models ($R^2=.17$ to
 292 $.21$), and only moderately higher when restricted to countries approaching elimination in
 293 Columns 4-6 ($R^2=.41$ to $.45$). For malaria control (columns 1-3), both backward stepwise and
 294 grid search models showed a positive relationship between progress and hospital capacity
 295 ($p=.041$ for backwards; $p=.014$ for grid search); however, no health systems features showed a
 296 statistically significant relationship with malaria control in the model including all 7
 297 components. For malaria elimination (columns 4-6), greater primary health center density was
 298 associated with decreased probability of reaching zero cases ($p=.027$ for all 7 components
 299 model; $p=.014$ for backward stepwise and grid search). Hospital capacity was positively
 300 correlated with malaria elimination, but this result was only statistically significant the

301 backwards stepwise and grid search models ($p=.007$). In addition, elimination appeared
 302 slightly negatively associated with good governance in all models, though this result was not
 303 statistically significant.

304 **Table 3: Regression Model Results (coefficients and R-squared) for malaria case**
 305 **reductions and health system components, 2000-2016.**

Health System Component	Percent reduction in cases per capita, 2000-2016 (β)			Reached 0 cases by 2016 (β) [Low burden countries only]		
	All	Backward Stepwise	Grid Search	All	Backward Stepwise	Grid Search
1 Health service delivery, routine services	4.2	5.1	4.9	-0.05	Not selected.	Not selected.
2 Access to medicines	4.3	Not selected.	Not selected.	-0.13	Not selected.	Not selected.
3 Health system workforce	0.6	Not selected.	Not selected.	0.02	Not selected.	Not selected.
4 Health system capacity: health centers	6.7	Not selected.	6.6	-0.10*	-0.10*	-0.10*
5 Health system capacity: hospitals	6.1	9.9*	6.9*	0.18	0.20**	0.20**
6 Governance	1.0	Not selected.	Not selected.	-0.05	-0.08	-0.08
7 Health information systems	-0.5	Not selected.	Not selected.	0.27	Not selected.	Not selected.
R ² for model:	.20	.17	.20	.45	.41	.41

Notes: All regressions adjust for HDI in 2000 and total health expenditure as percentage of GDP. Percent reduction models (columns I-III) also control for initial malaria burden category. Backward stepwise models exclude variables with $p>0.2$ and include variables with p -values < 0.10 . Grid search results reflect the model with lowest root mean squared error, among all models including up to 7 components.

[†]The analysis conducted only among countries in the low burden category (<1 case per 1000 in 2000).

*: Variable is significant at $p<.05$; **: Variable is significant at $p<.01$

306 In the high burden category, health systems factors predicted progress in malaria
 307 control relatively well ($R^2=.71$). Table 4 gives the model results stratified by initial malaria
 308 burden category. Among high burden countries, health service delivery and hospital capacity

309 were strongly positively predictive of malaria progress: on average each standard deviation
 310 increase in ability to deliver services was associated with an additional 17 percentage point
 311 reduction malaria cases ($p<.001$). Hospital density and capacity also showed a strong positive
 312 correlation with reduction in malaria cases ($p<.001$). Health information systems (including
 313 completeness of birth registration and malaria reporting) were negatively associated with
 314 malaria progress ($p=.003$), potentially due to some interdependence between completeness of
 315 malaria reporting and increased reporting of malaria cases. Among low and middle burden
 316 countries, health system factors had more limited power in predicting progress in malaria
 317 control ($R^2=.26$ and $.16$, respectively), and no health systems factors displayed statistically
 318 significant associations with progress in malaria control. In low burden counties, health center
 319 density appeared negatively associated with progress, though this result was not statistically
 320 significant at standard cutoffs ($p=.052$).

321 **Table 4: Backward stepwise regression model results (coefficients and R-squared) for**
 322 **malaria case reductions and health system components, 2000-2016, stratified by burden**
 323 **category.**

Health System Component	Percent reduction in cases per capita, 2000-2016 (β)			Reached 0 cases by 2016 (β)
	Low	Middle	High	Low
Initial Burden Category [†]				
1 Health service delivery, routine services	Not selected.	Not selected.	17.2**	Not selected.
2 Access to medicines	-12.4	12.1	Not selected.	Not selected.
3 Health system workforce	Not selected.	Not selected.	Not selected.	Not selected.
4 Health system capacity: health centers	-2.0	20.0	Not selected.	-0.10*
5 Health system capacity: hospitals	5.6	Not selected.	6.6**	0.20**
6 Governance	Not selected.	Not selected.	-4.5	-0.08
7 Health information systems	Not selected.	Not selected.	-9.3**	Not selected.
R ² for backward stepwise model:	.26	.16	.70	.41

Notes: All regressions adjust for HDI in 2000 and total health expenditure as percentage of GDP. Backward stepwise models exclude variables with $p > 0.2$ and include variables with p -values $< .1$.

[†]Initial Burden Category is defined as: Low = < 1 case per 1000 in 2000, Middle = 1-300 cases per 1000 in 2000, High = 300+ cases per 1000 in 2000

*: Variable is significant at $p < .05$; **: Variable is significant at $p < .01$

324 Discussion

325 This study used all currently available quantitative data to identify the health systems
326 factors most relevant for malaria control. While several factors were found to be associated
327 with progress in malaria control, observed associations were highly heterogeneous overall,
328 with no single factor or threshold predicting malaria control progress across all burden groups.
329 In general, countries that were malaria endemic in 2000 and achieved zero malaria cases by
330 2016 had relatively high health systems scores (Figure 5). However, when other contextual
331 factors were controlled for, the predictive power of health systems factors was relatively
332 limited (Table 3). The descriptive analysis presented in this paper also makes it clear that
333 rather remarkable progress has been made in several countries with very weak health systems.
334 One of the primary reasons why this may be the case is the largely vertical nature of many
335 national malaria programs. Prior research shows that the interventions responsible for the
336 greatest malaria reductions during this period have been vector control programs (foremost
337 distribution of ITNs, as well as IRS campaigns) [41], which are often delivered through
338 vertical processes by organizations external to national health systems [42,43]. These
339 heterogeneous results highlight that context-specific health system strengthening approaches
340 are needed for malaria control and elimination.

341 Investments in health systems are already considered an important aspect of malaria
342 control programs [44]. In its eighth round of funding, the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, TB and
343 Malaria, which provides 96% of external malaria funding, allocated 37% (US\$362 million) of
344 its overall funding towards health systems strengthening – of which US\$139 million went
345 towards general health systems support and the remaining went to disease-specific system
346 strengthening [45]. The vast majority (82%) of overall health systems funding went towards

347 three building blocks: service delivery, human resources and medicines [45]. Among low
348 burden countries approaching elimination, the large majority of external financing in countries
349 goes towards vertical interventions including treatment, diagnosis and vector control, though
350 the portion allocated for health system strengthening is growing [46].

351 High-burden countries, which generally tend to have weaker health systems, may see
352 the largest benefits from health systems strengthening interventions. Amid recent increases in
353 cases between 2015 and 2017 especially among the highest burden countries [38],
354 revitalization of malaria control approaches are needed in these countries. After restricting the
355 adjusted analysis to high burden countries, health systems displayed strong correlations with
356 progress in malaria control. These findings are inconsistent with a mostly theoretical literature
357 which suggests that research and investments in health systems are likely to have a larger
358 impact in middle-burden countries rather than in low- or high-burden countries [47].
359 Specifically, among high-burden countries service delivery and hospital-level infrastructure
360 appear to be most predictive of malaria control progress (Table 4). This appears well aligned
361 with the Global Fund's current focus on routine service delivery, including investments in
362 quality improvement as well as infrastructure [44].

363 In low and middle burden countries, health systems factors overall have much lower
364 predictive power for progress in malaria control and moderately more for elimination. In low
365 burden countries approaching elimination, greater density of lower level health facilities
366 appeared negatively correlated with elimination – however these results were heavily
367 influenced by China, Mexico, and South Korea which all had high coverage of health
368 facilities but did not eliminate malaria and had large reductions in malaria burden (>99%,
369 94%, and 87%, respectively); this may be an indication of more highly developed health
370 systems having stronger surveillance systems and therefore being less likely to have reported
371 zero cases in 2016. In addition, hospital capacity (including density of hospitals and hospital
372 beds) appeared to play a role –likely related to former Soviet countries (Azerbaijan,

373 Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan) which traditionally had a hospital-centered systems and achieved zero
374 indigenous cases of malaria during this time frame. Finally, all models for low burden
375 countries displayed a negative (but not significant) relationship between governance and
376 malaria elimination, potentially driven by some successful malaria campaigns in countries
377 which scored poorly on governance due to political instability and lack of freedom of
378 expression (e.g. Syria, Iraq, Algeria). This apparent negative relationship with governance is
379 consistent with a detailed case review of nine malaria elimination programs which found that
380 countries which had clearer lines of accountability and responsibilities (e.g. in Turkey and
381 Turkmenistan) had more successful campaigns [48].

382 The analysis presented was limited by the quality of data on malaria and health
383 systems in several ways. First, the malaria incidence data analyzed depend on local
384 surveillance capacity, and likely do not capture all cases in many countries. This should not
385 affect the main results since the primary outcome analyzed was changes over time within
386 countries. Second, the more than 20 data publically available health systems data sources
387 continue to have insufficient coverage for a time-series analysis, which means that period
388 averages have to be used instead of year-specific health system measures. Beyond the inherent
389 challenges in quantitatively disentangling the complex relationship between health systems
390 and other social and ecological factors important for malaria control, the static nature of the
391 data meant that it was not possible to draw causal inference. There is a critical need for better
392 and more consistent data on health systems at the country level which inform on the strength
393 and process of the health system [23,24]. Several health systems variables that are potentially
394 important for malaria control such as medicines availability at Primary Health Care Centers
395 were entirely excluded due to lack of data coverage. The Service Provision Assessment (SPA)
396 and Service Availability and Readiness Assessment (SARA) surveys present opportunities to
397 better understand country health systems as well as the impact of these factors on malaria
398 control, but are currently only available for 8 and 13 countries, respectively [49,50]. Higher

399 quality data across countries will allow for additional more nuanced assessments of health
400 systems readiness for disease control initiatives as well as better monitoring of their health
401 systems impact.

402 **Conclusions**

403 The results presented in this paper highlight the large heterogeneity in the progress made in
404 malaria control during the period 2000 to 2016, as well as the large heterogeneity in countries'
405 current health systems infrastructure. While many factors appear relevant for malaria control,
406 the results presented here that there is no single health systems factor or threshold that
407 dominates other factors in countries' ability to move towards elimination. Additional health
408 systems strengthening support will likely have the largest impact in high-burden countries,
409 especially in the domain of service delivery.

410 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

411 Not applicable.

412 **Consent for publication**

413 Not applicable.

414 **Availability of data and materials**

415 All data used in this analysis are publicly available - full references are provided in the
416 Appendix. The compiled dataset analyzed for the study is available upon request.

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419 **Competing interests**

420 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

421 **Authors' contributions**

422 GF, FT, AN, JJ and MS conceived of the study and the analytical framework. MS and JJ
423 extracted data, and MS constructed the final database. GF and MS conducted the analysis,
424 produced tables and figures, and drafted the manuscript. MS generated appendices. FT, AN

425 and JJ provided analytical support and manuscript review. All authors read and approved of
426 the final manuscript.

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